

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933 Call: HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01

Type of action: CSA

standICT²⁰²⁶.eu

ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

D3.1 Call Monitoring Report 1

Work package	WP3 “Management facility for EU experts in ICT standardisation “The StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme””
Task	Task 3.1 – Open Calls management for participation in SDO activities
Due date	30/11/2023
Submission date	20/12/2023
Deliverable lead	Trust-IT
Version	1.0
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Executive Summary	Included
Keywords	open calls, external evaluators, standardisation specialists, ICT Rolling Plan, ICT Standards

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributors
0.1	27.11.2023	Table of Contents, Section 1	Patricia Nugent (Trust-IT)
0.2	13.12.2023	Section 2 and 3s	Patricia Nugent (Trust-IT)
0.3	13.12.2023	Section 5	Mona Marill (AUS)
0.4	15.12.2023	Section 4, Executive Summary and Conclusions	Patricia Nugent (Trust-IT)
0.5	18.12.2023	Issue for Peer Review	
	19.12.2023	Peer Review	Knut Blind (Fraunhofer) Mona Marill (AUS)
0.6	19.12.2023	<i>Comments incorporated and final quality check</i>	Maria Giuffrida, Gabriele Quattrocchi (Trust-IT)
1.0	20.12.2023	<i>Submission</i>	Sharon Farrel (DCU)

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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A total of **188 eligible proposals** were submitted the first two open calls of StandICT.eu 2023 for a total amount of requested funding of over **1.74 MEURO**. Applicants represented **23 EU Members States and associated countries** and covered a broad range of the priority topics of the calls. The **72 successful applicants** were funded for a cumulative total of **657,684 EURO in financial support**. Activities funded covered **20 different priority topics** with *Artificial Intelligence* accounting for the largest number (20 out of 41 proposals funded over Open call (OC) 1 and 2), followed by *Network and Information Security*, *Cybersecurity* and *Quantum Technology*. Of the recently introduced topics, it can be noted that Metaverse is attracting a steady increase in the number of applications submitted (4 out of 10 proposals funded over OC1 and OC2).

The quality of the proposals was also extremely high with the average score of proposals over the funding threshold at **8.94 out of a possible 10 points for OC1** and for **8.63 out of a possible 10 points for OC2** and an overall average score of the funded applicants for both calls of **8.80**.

It is an undeniable fact that the open calls emphasize the **truly global reach** of the European specialists in shaping and supporting European policies, regulation and strategies within ICT standards with **over two-thirds of all funded applicants contributing to International Standards Organisations**, including ISO, ISO/IEC, IEC, ITU, IEEE, and IETF; and the remainder to ESOs (ETSI, CEN or CEN/CENELEC) or to cross-SDO collaboration.

This deliverable, D3.1 “Call Monitoring Report 1”, is released at the end of Month 12 and describes activities related to the **StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme, a series of nine open calls which will provide € 2,925,000 of EU funding earmarked to support the global reach of European ICT standardisation specialists in the European ICT Standardisation Ecosystem** through 9 Open Calls to be delivered over the lifetime of the project.

This comprises selection of the open call topics, in alignment with the **MSP Rolling Plan of ICT Standardisation**, selection and management of the External Pool of Evaluators (EPE) which falls under the remit of Task 1.4, the outcomes of OC1, OC2 and the status of OC3 which closes on the 9th of January, as well as the fellowship monitoring activities and reporting using a results-oriented approach which will continue to show more impact as the first two batches of funded projects come to a close.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	Explanation
AUS	AUSTRALO Interinnov Marketing Lab (Project Partner=)
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DCU	Dublin City University (Project Financial and Administrative Coordinator)
EAG	External Advisory Group
EUOS	European Observatory for ICT Standards
Grants Platform	The Trust-IT Services Grants Platform
MSP	European Multi-Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardisation
MSs	Member States
NSB	National Standard Bodies
OC	Open Call(s)
SDO	Standard Developing Organisations
TWG	Technical Working Group
TRUST-IT	Trust-IT Services Srl (Project Technical Coordinator)
LT	Long-term fellowship
ST	Short-term fellowship
OS	One-shot fellowship

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This deliverable, “D3.1 Call Monitoring Report 1”, submitted at Month 12 of the Project, describes the outcomes of the submissions to Open Call 1 and Open Call 2 to the StandICT.eu 2026 open calls for ICT Standardisation Experts in their respective fields, the recruitment of the external experts for the evaluation of the open calls, who come together as the External Pool of Evaluators (EPE) and the work that they have performed work, as well as the selection of the priority topics for the open calls.

This deliverable was initially intended to cover to cover the results of the third open call. However, as the timings of the calls were adjusted to avoid any overlaps with the pre-cursor StandICT.eu 2023 project, the third open call is still open at the time of writing and submission and will close on the 9th of January 2024. The deliverable is also a few weeks late with respect to the M11 deadline to accommodate the results of the second open call.

As a further two iterations of this document are foreseen over the course of the Project (D3.2 and D3.4), this deliverable be incremental in content up to the last and final call so that all of the information related to the open calls are readily available for consultation in its latest version.

1.2 Structure

The document is divided in the following sections:

- *Section 2* provides a statistical overview of the applications received and funding granted through the 2 open calls closed and evaluated at the time of writing and information on the launch of Open Call 3, closing on the 9th of January, as well as an overview of the opening and closing dates of the calls to project end with the relevant funding assigned and allocated
- *Section 3* provides a report on the composition and management of the External Pool of Evaluators (EPE) engaged under contract by StandICT.eu, as part of Task 1.4.
- *Section 4* focuses on the applications received, providing details on the ranking and related applicants.
- *Section 5* provides information on the monitoring of the projects funded.
- *Section 6* provides conclusions and lessons learned

The following StandICT.eu 2026 deliverables which are related to this document are the following:

- D6.1 Plan for communication & stakeholder engagement strategy & plan and promotion of the open call

2. SUMMARY OUTCOMES OF THE OPEN CALLS

2.1 Open Call Priority Topics

The priority topics of the StandICT.eu 2026 open Calls, which are set out in Figure 1 below, are closely correlated to the list of priority areas of the [European Multi-Stakeholder Platform \(MSP\) on ICT Standardisation Rolling Plan](#), currently in its 2023 edition. The macro areas of the Rolling Plan include the four main EU Policies supported by ICT Standardisation: Foundational Drivers; Key Enablers; Societal Challenges; Innovation for the Digital Single Market, and Sustainable Growth, with each topic comprising multiple sub-categories. The Rolling Plan also references new relevant legislative acts such as the Data Act, Digital Services Act (DSA), Digital Markets Act (DMA) or the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA).

- | | |
|---|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FOUNDATIONAL DRIVERS ○ <i>Data Economy</i> ○ <i>Cybersecurity/Network and Information security</i> ○ <i>E-Privacy</i> • KEY ENABLERS ○ <i>5G and Beyond (6G)</i> ○ <i>Cloud and Edge Computing</i> ○ <i>Big Data & Open data</i> ○ <i>IoT Internet of Things</i> ○ <i>Electronic identification and trust services (including e-signature)</i> ○ <i>E-infrastructure for data and computing intensive service</i> ○ <i>Broadband infrastructure mapping</i> ○ <i>Accessibility of ICT products and services</i> ○ <i>Artificial Intelligence</i> ○ <i>European Global Navigation Satellite Systems (EGNSS)</i> ○ <i>Quantum Technologies</i> • SOCIETAL CHALLENGES ○ <i>E-Health, Healthy living and ageing</i> ○ <i>Digital skills</i> ○ <i>Digital learning</i> ○ <i>E-Government</i> ○ <i>E-call</i> ○ <i>Pandemic Preparedness</i> ○ <i>Safety, transparency and due process online</i> | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Emergency communications and public warning systems</i> • INNOVATION FOR THE DIGITAL SINGLE MARKET ○ <i>E-Procurement</i> ○ <i>E-Invoicing</i> ○ <i>Retail payments</i> ○ <i>Preservation of digital cinema</i> ○ <i>FinTech & RegTech Standardisation</i> ○ <i>Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies</i> ○ <i>Metaverse including Civerse</i> ○ • SUSTAINABLE GROWTH ○ <i>Smart Grids and Smart Metering</i> ○ <i>Smart and Sustainable Cities</i> ○ <i>ICT Environmental impact</i> ○ <i>European Electronic Toll Service (EETS)</i> ○ <i>Intelligent Transport Systems</i> ○ <i>Digitisation of European Industry</i> ○ <i>Robotics and autonomous systems</i> ○ <i>Construction building information modelling</i> ○ <i>Common information sharing environment (CISE) for the EU Maritime domain</i> ○ <i>Water management digitalisation</i> ○ <i>Single European Sky</i> ○ <i>U-Space</i> ○ <i>Circular Economy including Digital Product Passport</i> |
|---|---|

FIGURE 1 - OPEN CALL TOPICS FOR CALLS 1-3

The priority topics are continuously monitored vis-à-vis European Commission objectives to ensure that the financial resources deriving from the open calls are strategically channelled to sectors and areas where additional presence of EU Member States and Associated Countries may be needed. This is a continuous, virtuous cycle driven by the influential StandICT.eu Forum for European Strategy on ICT Standards (FOREST), managed under Task 6.3, and

coalescing efforts of the External Advisory Group (EAG, the Technical Working Groups managed under *Task 2.1 EUOS Observatory and Technical Working Groups*, and the funded fellows.

2.1 Summary Outcome of OC 1

FIGURE 2 – OPEN CALL 1 BANNER

OC1 opened on the 8th of May and closed on the 10th of July 2023. Figure 3 below provides a breakdown of the proposals funded by topic addressed and the SDOs to which the fellows are contributing, as well as their organisation type, while Figure 4 shows how the funded applications fit within the MSP Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation.

FIGURE 3 - BREAKDOWN OF FUNDED PROPOSALS BY TOPIC OC 1

FIGURE 4 - FUNDED TOPICS BY ICT STANDARDISATION ROLLING PLAN OC 1

2.2 Summary Outcome of OC 2

FIGURE 5 – OPEN CALL 2 BANNER

OC2 opened on the 31st of July and closed on the 2nd of October 2023. Figure 6 below provides a breakdown of the proposals funded by topic addressed and the SDOs to which the fellows are contributing, as well as their organisation type, while Figure 7 shows how the funded applications fit within the MSP Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation.

FIGURE 6 – BREAKDOWN OF FUNDED PROPOSALS BY TOPIC OC 2

FIGURE 7 – FUNDED TOPICS BY ICT STANDARDISATION ROLLING PLAN OC 2

2.3 Interim Information on OC 3

FIGURE 8 - OPEN CALL 3 BANNER

As explained in the above, this deliverable was initially intended to cover to cover third open call. However, as the timings of the calls of StandICT.eu 2026 were adjusted to avoid any overlaps with the pre-cursor StandICT.eu 2023 project, the third open call was launched on the 30th of October 2023, as shown in the call banner in Figure 8 and will close on the 9th of January 2024.

At the time of writing, 30 proposals have been submitted and/or are in draft on the platform and, therefore, there is not yet a sufficient number to formulate any statistics on this basis. However, this is fully in line with what is normally to be observed, as applications usually trickle in slowly over the first month to increase steadily over the second month and peak during the final week, and in particular over the last available weekend prior to call closure.

2.4 Call timings and Funding

Table 1 below presents the financial status in terms of allocated budget for Open Calls 1 and 2, as well as the scheduled call timings and the projected funding for each open call which is the average amount of the remaining budget subdivided by call.

The allocated funding will be closely monitored to ensure that any remaining funding with respect to the amount projected for each call is re-allocated under the subsequent calls to project completion, ensuring that all of the Financial Support for Third Parties available is utilised while not compromising the high quality of the proposals selected.

The former is a contingency for those cases where an applicant does not fulfil their reporting obligations with StandICT.eu 2026, or otherwise does not carry out the work pursuant to award and is closely tied to the monitoring activities carried out on the fellowship as further described in Section 5.

Call No.	Opening Date	Closing Date	Grant Type	Funded Fellows	Allocated Funding	Projected Funding	Cumulative Total
1	08/05/2023	10/07/2023	LT, ST	35	€ 331,766.00		€ 331,766.00
2	31/07/2023	02/10/2023	LT, ST	37	€ 325,918.00		€ 657,684.00
3	30/10/2023	09/01/2024	LT, ST, OS			€ 323,902.35	€ 981.585,87
4	12/02/2024	12/04/2024	LT, ST, OS			€ 323,902.35	€ 1.305.488,23
5	29/04/2024	28/06/2024	LT, ST, OS			€ 323,902.35	€ 1.629.390,58
6	08/07/2024;	13/09/2024	LT, ST, OS			€ 323,902.35	€ 1.953.292,94
7	23/09/2024	22/11/2024	LT, ST, OS			€ 323,902.35	€ 2.277.195,29
8	02/12/2024	03/02/2025	LT, ST, OS			€ 323,902.35	€ 2.601.097,65
9	17/02/2025	18/04/2025	LT, ST, OS			€ 323,902.35	€ 2.925.000,00

TABLE 1 – CALL TIMINGS, FUNDED PROPOSALS AND PROJECTED BUDGET

3. EXTERNAL POOL OF EVALUATORS

In accordance with the Grant Agreement, the evaluation of the applications received in response to the open calls is outsourced to a group of external experts in ICT standardisation who come together as the StandICT.eu External Pool of Experts, or EPE.

The EPE are also selected via an open call process to ensure an impartial, transparent and consistent review process of the applications received. The open call for evaluators was launched on the 31st of March and closed on the 31st of May 2023 with the possibility to re-open a reserve call at a later stage in the project to compensate for retiring members, changes in or broader coverage of the priority topics. The banner for the open call for Evaluators is shown in Figure 9 below.

FIGURE 9 - OPEN CALL EPE

3.1 Composition of the EPE

131 eligible applications were received in response to the call, of which 23 were from the precursor StandICT.eu 2023 project. The applications were evaluated in two batches to enable a first batch of successful applicants to be onboarded and under contract in time for closure of the first open call for funding.

The applications to the EPE call were evaluated on the basis of a three Partner, blind vote from the two academic Partners DCU and Fraunhofer plus Trust-IT via the Grants Platform. The evaluation was based on information provided in the application form and proven expertise in ICT standardisation and the open call priority topics demonstrated on a supporting cv. Applicants receiving three favourable votes from the Project Partners were selected to the Pool with those achieving two votes placed on a reserve list.

From evaluation of the 1st batch of 53 applications 44 of the applicants receiving 3 supporting votes went to contract and in advance of OC1 closure. Two of these members have since resigned taking the first batch placed under contract to 42.

Of the remaining applications voted in a second batch, a further 14 applicants received three positive votes and are being contracted to provide additional support from OC 3.

This takes the current overall number to 56 at the time of writing, achieving the objective of 50+ members with a wide geographical and priority topic coverage.

As to gender balance, more female candidates were successful in the application phase than male and therefore were more represented proportionally in respect to the overall number of applications received from female applicants.

A list of the current EPE is provided in Table 1. Given the public dissemination level of this deliverable, this information is limited to proposal ID and contract number name (where applicable), surname, gender country. Please note that this list is inclusive of any names approved under the second batch yet to be contracted for OC3 and the two members who have resigned.

No.	Proposal ID	Contract No.	Surname, Name	Gender	Country	Status
1	EPE-082	01/38	Aileni, Raluca Maria	F	RO	Approved, under contact
2	EPE-016	01/01	Amato, Paola	F	IT	Approved, under contact
3	EPE-140	N/A	Azpúrua, Marco	M	ES	Approved, to be contracted
4	EPE-077	01/21	Badea, Ana-Cornelia	F	RO	Approved, under contact
5	EPE-030	01/03	Boumbarova, Neviana	F	BG	Approved, under contact
6	EPE-149	N/A	Burgos, Daniel	M	ES	Approved, to be contracted
7	EPE-027	01/17	Cadzow, Scott	M	UK	Approved, under contact
8	EPE-032	01/04	Campegiani, Paolo	M	IT	Approved, under contact

9	EPE-026	01/02	Carmona, Eduardo	M	ES	Approved, under contact
10	EPE-050	01/39	Castellanos, Javier	M	ES	Approved, under contact
11	EPE-086	01/16	Cenkier, Grzegorz	M	PL	Approved, under contact
12	EPE-054	01/28	Chkhaidze, Nanuli	M	GE	Approved, under contact
13	EPE-151	N/A	Contreras, Luis Miguel	M	ES	Approved, to be contracted
14	EPE-073	01/43	Cotton, Paul	M	CA	Approved, under contact
15	EPE-033	01/05	Dacal, Angel	M	ES	Approved, under contact
16	EPE-113	01/33	Dagiuklas, Tasos	M	UK	Approved, under contact
17	EPE-103	01/30	de la Feld, Marco	M	IT	Approved, under contact
18	EPE-154	N/A	Dhaher, Omar	M	BE	Approved, to be contracted
19	EPE-159	N/A	Dimitriadis, Athanasios	M	GR	Approved, to be contracted
20	EPE-161	N/A	Flynn, Bob	M	UK	Approved, to be contracted
21	EPE-112	01/32	Frascolla, Valerio	M	DE	Approved, under contact
22	EPE-049	01/10	Gaur, Sachin	M	NO	Approved, under contact
23	EPE-162	N/A	Giribaldi, Davide	M	CH	Approved, to be contracted

24	EPE-079	01/44	Hoeckner, Klaus	M	AT	Approved, under contact
25	EPE-164	N/A	Hubert, Pascal	M	FR	Approved, to be contracted
26	EPE-090	01/25	Iglesias, Josue	M	AT	Approved, under contact
27	EPE-165	N/A	Kaliampakas, Efthymios	M	GR	Approved, to be contracted
28	EPE-168	N/A	Lanting, Cornelis J.M.	M	BE	Approved, to be contracted
29	EPE-098	01/26	Lemic, Filip	M	BE	Approved, under contact
30	EPE-123	01/35	Magistrelli, Giorgio	M	BE	Approved, under contact
31	EPE-061	01/14	Marsal, Maria Luisa	M	ES	Approved, under contact
32	EPE-169	N/A	Massimo, Fabio	M	IT	Approved, to be contracted
33	EPE-102	01/27	Milicevic, Kruno	M	HR	Approved, under contact
34	EPE-087	01/22	Mrak, Marta	F	UK	Approved, under contact
35	EPE-034	01/06	Nikolaou, Nikolaos	M	DE	Approved, under contact
36	EPE-037	01/08	Pandey, Pankaj	M	NO	Approved, under contact
37	EPE-072	01/15	Pasic, Aljosa	M	ES	Approved, under contact
38	EPE-069	01/36	Pastore, Serena	F	IT	Approved, under contact

39	EPE-057	01/13	Pavleska, Tanja	F	SI	Approved, under contact
40	EPE-065	01/37	Perea, Carmen	F	ES	Approved, under contact
	EPE-031	01/19	Phipps, Simon	M	UK	Resigned
41	EPE-023	01/20	Prasad, Venkatesha	M	NL	Approved, under contact
42	EPE-051	01/11	Renwick, Robin Renwick	M	IE	Approved, under contact
43	EPE-174	01/45	Rogers, Heather	F	ES	Approved, under contact
44	EPE-172	N/A	Rogers, Heather	F	ES	Approved, to be contracted
45	EPE-021	01/34	Roseiro, Pedro	M	PT	Approved, under contact
46	EPE-109	01/31	Ruffini, sergio	M	IT	Approved, under contact
47	EPE-035	01/07	Salis, Antonio	M	IT	Approved, under contact
48	EPE-056	01/41	Sulzer, Jean-Francois	M	FR	Approved, under contact
49	EPE-053	01/18	Terseglav, Gaber	M	SI	Approved, under contact
	EPE-052	01/12	Trenta, Andrea	M	IT	Resigned
50	EPE-173	N/A	Tsekeridou, Sofia	F	GR	Approved, to be contracted
51	EPE-046	01/09	Velasco, Luis	M	ES	Approved, under contact
52	EPE-074	01/42	Wild, Fridolin	M	UK	Approved, under contact

53	EPE-060	01/29	Wolf, Andreas	M	DE	Approved, under contact
54	EPE-174	N/A	Wood, Suno	F	UK	Approved, to be contracted
55	EPE-088	01/23	Yonchina, Pavlina	F	BG	Approved, under contact
56	EPE-089	01/24	Ziegler, Wolfgang	M	DE	Approved, under contact

TABLE 2 – EPE LIST

3.2 EPE Assignment and Assessment of the work performed

The EPE accepted and under contract with StandICT.eu are mapped in terms of their competency on the priority topics of the open calls to match them to the applications received, while being sure to maintain a good geographical balance and gender balance where possible.

After initial eligibility screening three different evaluators are assigned to each proposal, of which one acts as Rapporteur. A fourth evaluator is selected from the pool to act as Quality Controller. The assignments are made on the Grants Platform, where the online evaluation process takes place following the workflow shown in Figure 10 below, while an exhaustive explanation of each step is provided to the evaluators via a Briefing Pack made available via a reserved space on the StandICT.eu 2026 website. This is updated, if necessary, following each call to incorporate any feedback provided by the evaluators, or any other issues that may have emerged during the evaluations.

In summary, each individual evaluator accesses the proposals assigned via their dashboard and submits an Individual Evaluation Report (IER), after which the evaluator acting as Rapporteur summarises and merges the comments of the three and submits Evaluation Summary Report (ESR) to the system, shared automatically with the other two evaluators involved for consensus. Consensus takes place via a dedicated chat function visible for each proposal to which the evaluators and the Quality Controller are signed. The final, agreed version is saved as the Consensus Report which then becomes visible to the Quality Controller for final review. The Quality Controller checks the scores, comments and consensus in the chat and approves or rejects the final version with the reasons for rejection. In case of rejection, the Consensus Report reverts to the Rapporteur for re-working, or a change of score, if necessary, in agreement with the other two evaluators.

FIGURE 10 – EVALUATION WORKFLOW

Once the process has been completed, the Call Administrator ensures that all documentation has been correctly submitted using a dedicated evaluation status menu visible their dashboard as shown in Figure 11 below. This menu is also used to monitor the progress of the ongoing evaluations and to guarantee completely transparent and traceable information relevant to each single phase of the evaluation workflow.

FIGURE 11 – EVALUATION STATUS MENU

After ranking of the proposals, each of the applicants are notified personally of the outcome of their proposal via email and can access the Consensus Report via their dashboard.

Applicants to a call have 5 business days after notification of the outcome of their proposal to present a redress request.

Redress requests are considered solely based on the procedural aspects of the process, and not on merit. This is based on the principle that the StandICT.eu evaluations are **outsourced to the EPE to guarantee full impartiality** and that **all evaluators have been selected as experts in their field through an open call process** where their competency has already been verified and adhere to **strict Conflict-of-Interest clause as part of their contract which is further endorsed via the platform for each proposal accepted for evaluation**.

Further, each proposal is assigned to **three individual evaluators** for appraisal who assign a **set of individual blind votes**. This is followed by a **consensus phase** to ensure that **any major differences in scores and comments** are addressed and, above all, that any individual score likely to unfairly skew an overall score is dealt with. Following Consensus, all proposals undergo quality control by a fourth expert evaluator and all evaluators are selected through an open call process where their competency has already been verified and adhere to strict Conflict-of-Interest clause as part of their contract which is further endorsed via the platform for each proposal accepted for evaluation.

StandICT.eu 2026 received three redress requests to OC1 and two to OC2 where a full review of the process of each received for OC1 has been performed and documented and the applicants informed of the outcome.

3.3 EPE Payments

The External Pool of Evaluators are paid at a daily rate of 400 Euro, or 50 Euro per hour. Each evaluator is paid 30 minutes for each proposal evaluated, including interaction with the other evaluators during consensus, 20 minutes for each Rapporteur role and 20 mins for Quality Control. This equates to an overall cost of 108.33 Euro per proposal evaluation as shown in Table 3 below.

Overall cost of each proposal evaluated	
<i>3 Evaluations (30 mins) including consensus phase</i>	75.00 €
<i>1 Rapporteur (20 mins)</i>	16.67 €
<i>1 Quality Control (20 mins)</i>	16.67 €
Total	108.33 €

TABLE 3 – COST OF EVALUATION PER APPLICATION

A list of the payments made to the EPE for OC 1 and OC 2 is provided in Table 4 below.

No.	EPE ID	Surname, Name	Amount
1	EPE-082	Aileni, Raluca Maria	541,69 €
2	EPE-016	Amato, Paola	441,72 €

No.	EPE ID	Surname, Name	Amount
3	EPE-077	Badea, Ana-Cornelia	158,34 €
4	EPE-030	Boumbarova, Neviana	125,00 €

No.	EPE ID	Surname, Name	Amount
6	EPE-027	Cadzow, Scott	883,41 €
7	EPE-032	Campegiani, Paolo	250,01 €
8	EPE-026	Carmona, Eduardo	233,36 €
9	EPE-050	Castellanos, Javier	341,68 €
10	EPE-086	Cenkier, Grzegorz	433,35 €
11	EPE-054	Chkhaidze, Nanuli	275,00 €
12	EPE-033	Dacal, Angel	933,41 €
13	EPE-113	Dagiuklas, Tasos	825,07 €
14	EPE-103	de la Feld, Marco	491,68 €
15	EPE-112	Frascolla, Valerio	258,34 €
16	EPE-049	Gaur, Sachin	258,34 €
17	EPE-079	Hoeckner, Klaus	91,67 €
18	EPE-090	Iglesias, Josue	408,38 €
19	EPE-098	Lemic, Filip	450,02 €
20	EPE-123	Magistrelli, Giorgio	700,04 €
21	EPE-061	Marsal, Maria Luisa	208,34 €
22	EPE-102	Milicevic, Kruno	550,02 €
23	EPE-087	Mrak, Marta	300,01 €
24	EPE-034	Nikolaou, Nikolaos	691,70 €
25	EPE-037	Pandey, Pankaj	566,69 €

No.	EPE ID	Surname, Name	Amount
26	EPE-072	Pasic, Aljosa	400,00 €
27	EPE-069	Pastore, Serena	658,39 €
28	EPE-057	Pavleska, Tanja	225,01 €
29	EPE-065	Perea, Carmen	691,72 €
30	EPE-031	Phipps, Simon	425,04 €
31	EPE-023	Prasad, Venkatesha	175,00 €
32	EPE-051	Renwick, Robin	816,74 €
33	EPE-174	Rogers, Heather	225,02 €
34	EPE-021	Roseiro, Pedro	866,74 €
35	EPE-109	Ruffini, sergio	358,37 €
36	EPE-035	Salis, Antonio	1.016,76 €
37	EPE-056	Sulzer, Jean-Francois	283,34 €
38	EPE-053	Terseglav, Gaber	133,34 €
39	EPE-052	Trenta, Andrea	166,67 €
40	EPE-046	Velasco, Luis	566,70 €
41	EPE-074	Wild, Fridolin	550,02 €
42	EPE-060	Wolf, Andreas	500,02 €
43	EPE-088	Yonchina, Pavlina	158,34 €
44	EPE-089	Ziegler, Wolfgang	800,06 €
Total Amount			19.434,55 €

TABLE 4 – PAYMENTS MADE TO THE EPE FOR OC 1 AND OC 2

Finally, pursuant to art. 204 of the EC financial regulations (Title VII, "Experts") and Art. 287 of the Rules of Application, paragraph 5, the list of the EPE members under contract with StandICT.eu 2026 that received compensations in 2023 is the above list which will be published on the StandICT.eu 2026 website at the beginning of 2024.

4. APPLICATIONS RECEIVED AND FUNDED

An overall total of **188 eligible applications** were submitted to OC 1 and OC 2. Overall, the standard of the proposals was extremely good resulting in **a total of 72 proposals funded over the two calls for a total of 657,684 Euro** in allocated funding and an average score of all funded proposals **of 8.80 out of a possible 10 marks**.

Once all applicants have been informed of on the outcome of their proposal, those successful are individually contacted by DCU, the Financial and Administrative Coordinator, outlining the paperwork necessary for the finance and payment process. This paperwork is completed and retained on file at the start of activities to guarantee a smooth payment process upon completion of the activities, acceptance of the reporting required and confirmation of the budgeted figures which are mandatory for payment. Information requested is kept to a minimum of the payee and payee address, bank details and a redacted bank statement or bank fee statement, confirming the bank details provided.

In parallel, the process to align the start and end dates for the fellowships, where necessary, and kick off monitoring activities carried out by AUS and the reporting to be provided fellows via their dashboard.

A full list of the applications received in response to OC 1 and OC 2, with proposal ID, score, and funding is provided in sub-sections 4.1-4.2 below, while details on the monitoring of each fellow, the status of their projects and their overall contributions is covered in Section 5.

4.1 Applications submitted and funded under OC 1

A full list of the eligible applications received to OC 1, including those not retained for funding, is provided in Table 5Table 1 below, in order of ranking with the proposal ID, the status of the fellowship at the time of writing, grant type and funding allocated.

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ¹	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
1	9.60	01-250	APR	Not for Profit Organisation	BE	Development of standards for AI enabled Photovoltaics	LT	€ 9,984
1	9.60	01-143	APR	SMEs	BE	Harmonised AI cybersecurity standards in response to the EC AI standardisation request	LT	€ 10,000
2	9.50	01-211	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	AI standardization roadmapping	LT	€ 10,000
3	9.40	01-256	APR	Government/Public Services	PT	Standards for Robotics and Autonomous Systems: Knowledge, Reasoning, Multiple Robots and HRI.	LT	€ 9,900
4	9.30	01-181	APR	Academia/Research	IT	Advancing the PWI on Competence Requirements for AI Ethics Professionals to the NWIP stage	LT	€ 8,900
4	9.30	01-185	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	SE	Consent records and privacy principles in eIDAS2 wallet	LT	€ 10,000
5	9.23	01-118	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	DE	Advance Biometric System-on-Card standard series ISO/IEC 17839	LT	€ 9,100

¹ APR -Approved; NAP – Not Approved; PAY – In Payment; CLO - Closed

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ¹	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
6	9.20	01-261	PAY	IT Consultancy/Development	BE	Contribution to e-identification and e-authentication at CEN/CLC/JTC 13 & ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 WG5's	ST	€ 4,909
6	9.20	01-208	APR	Academia/Research	IT	Effective Characterisation of Quantum Computing Systems	LT	€ 10,000
7	9.10	01-224	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	AT	Standardization of multiparty computation in ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 WG2	LT	€ 8,700
8	9.07	01-275	APR	SMEs	FR	Towards standards convergence for digital identity wallets	LT	€ 9,900
8	9.07	01-239	APR	SMEs	BE	Proposal for requirement regarding the elimination of publicly known exploitable vulnerabilities	LT	€ 10,000
9	9.00	01-285	APR	Academia/Research	NL	Philosophical Contributions on TS6254 - Explainability	LT	€ 9,869
10	8.98	01-144	APR	Academia/Research	ES	Environmental Sustainability for Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies	LT	€ 9,800
11	8.90	01-210	APR	Academia/Research	FR	Media Coding and API for Metaverse Interoperability	LT	€ 9,900
11	8.90	01-228	APR	Academia/Research	LU	IRTF NMRG agenda refinement for assessing and reducing the environmental impact of networking	LT	€ 10,000
12	8.87	01-222	APR	Academia/Research	UK	Leading the development of ITU standards for IoT applications in smart cities and communities	LT	€ 10,000

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ¹	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
12	8.87	01-117	APR	SMEs	UK	Support as Secretary for ETSI ISG SAI	LT	€ 10,000
12	8.87	01-264	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	GR	Develop scope & emerging requirements for new DLT & blockchain use-cases standards	LT	€ 10,000
12	8.87	01-232	APR	SMEs	BE	Participation in the development of standardisation work in support of RED Articles 3(3)(d/e/f)	LT	€ 10,000
13	8.85	01-212	APR	Government/Public Services	SE	Artificial Intelligence – Guidance on addressing societal concerns and ethical considerations	LT	€ 10,000
14	8.83	01-259	APR	Academia/Research	SE	Considerations for Multimodal and Interactive Artificial Intelligence	LT	€ 10,000
15	8.79	01-237	APR	Academia/Research	PL	O-RAN infrastructure evaluation tests	LT	€ 10,000
16	8.77	01-105	APR	SDO/National Standard Body	BE	Launching generalized quantum cryptography standardization	LT	€ 9,984
16	8.77	01-111	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	DE	Phase-2: STD Gen Framework: X-Dom Federated ETSI GANA KPs for 5G E2E Autonomic Security Man &Control	LT	€ 6,200
17	8.73	01-186	PAY	Government/Public Services	DK	Second edition of Rec. ITU-T X.510 ISO/IEC 9594-11	ST	€ 5,000
18	8.70	01-205	APR	Academia/Research	FI	Request for funding for IETF IoT work	LT	€ 9,820
19	8.65	01-218	APR	Academia/Research	RO	Contribution to AI-based Network Application standardization in 5G and beyond	LT	€ 9,900

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ¹	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
20	8.63	01-166	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	ES	Progress projects on logging and record keeping to support the AI Act	LT	€ 9,950
21	8.60	01-227	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	DK	Danish participation in the ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 32 WG 3 Database languages (SQL and GQL)	LT	€ 10,000
22	8.57	01-199	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	Journey Towards Ethical AI: A European Perspective on Nudging, Competence, and Ethics Roadmap.	LT	€ 10,000
22	8.57	01-180	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	UK	Standards for Information security and cloud service providers	LT	€ 10,000
22	8.57	01-099	APR	Academia/Research	ES	Accessibility in the Metaverse	LT	€ 9,950
22	8.57	01-233	APR	SMEs	FR	Security and privacy of biometrics for remote authentication	LT	€ 10,000
23	8.55	01-213	APR	SMEs	IE	Standards for Quantum Interconnect and Quantum Photonic Integrated Circuits	LT	€ 10,000
24	8.47	01-195	NAP	SMEs	FR	Contribute to prISO 16757-5	LT	€ 10,000
24	8.47	01-189	NAP	Academia/Research	FI	Contribution to ETSI TC SmartBAN	LT	€ 10,000
24	8.47	01-236	NAP	SMEs	UK	Technical Editor ISO/IEC 27566 Age Assurance Systems - Framework	LT	€ 10,000
25	8.43	01-247	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	DK	Key Management and Public-key infrastructure: Establishment and maintenance	LT	€ 10,000

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ¹	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
26	8.40	01-270	NAP	SMEs	FR	Strengthening AI security and privacy standards	LT	€ 10,000
26	8.40	01-267	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	LT	Advance on-card biometric comparison standards ISO/IEC 24787, ISO/IEC 17839, ISO/IEC 18584 series	LT	€ 10,000
27	8.35	01-252	NAP	SMEs	UK	Strategic Standards for Sustainable Growth (3SG) Project	LT	€ 10,000
28	8.33	01-238	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	UK	Towards a Committee Draft for ISO/IEC 23000-23 Decentralised Media Rights Application Format	LT	€ 10,000
29	8.31	01-243	NAP	SMEs	IT	DT-COOP: Standardizing Digital Twins Cooperation	LT	€ 10,000
30	8.25	01-282	NAP	SMEs	FR	Bridging the gap between EU R&I ecosystem and worldwide standardization on Smart Energy	LT	€ 10,000
31	8.23	01-193	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	AT	Inclusion of European values, Fundamental rights, and societal concerns in AI standardisation	LT	€ 10,000
32	8.20	01-216	NAP	Academia/Research	DE	Strengthening the EU Position in International Circular Economy Standards	ST	€ 10,000
32	8.20	01-220	NAP	Academia/Research	GR	Data and APIs in Smart City Platforms	LT	€ 10,000
33	8.14	01-263	NAP	SMEs	FR	Enhancing coordination between AI focussed Cybersecurity & Privacy standards with SC27/JTC21 AhG's	LT	€ 10,000

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ¹	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
34	8.13	01-262	NAP	Academia/Research	FR	Towards accurate, transparent and explainable systems in AI and NLP, in support of the AI Act	LT	€ 10,000
35	8.10	01-231	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	DE	Contribution to the CEN CENELEC Standard Request Ad-hoc group for Digital Product Passports	OS	€ 10,000
36	8.07	01-234	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	Rapid Electromagnetic Emission Check of Fixed Installations	LT	€ 10,000
37	8.00	01-271	NAP	Academia/Research	IT	Specification of ETSI MEC Sensor-sharing API	LT	€ 10,000
37	8.00	01-248	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	eID Wallet for the European citizen under the new eIDAS2	LT	€ 10,000
37	8.00	01-258	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	IE	laC Where Infrastructure meets Software Timeline (laC WHIST)	LT	€ 10,000
38	7.97	01-197	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	IT	Support CEN/CLC TR Data governance and quality for AI, fulfilling Rolling Plan ICT 2023	LT	€ 10,000
39	7.96	01-278	NAP	Academia/Research	IT	Standardizing the Quantum Internet	LT	€ 10,000
40	7.95	01-194	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	ES	Cybersecurity controls for Metaverse environments - Phase I	ST	€ 5,000
41	7.90	01-253	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	DE	Participation in CEN CENELEC Standard Request Ad-hoc group for Digital Product Passports	OS	€ 10,000
44	7.87	01-265	NAP	Policy/Funding Agency	UK	Developing the Strategy for Standards Development in ISO/TC307 Blockchain & DLT.	LT	€ 10,000

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ¹	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
42	7.85	01-230	NAP	Academia/Research	SE	Interoperable configuration and security attestation of Confidential Computing in the cloud	LT	€ 10,000
43	7.63	01-283	NAP	Large Enterprise	PL	Comparative analysis of standardisation of Trustworthy AI	LT	€ 10,000
44	7.60	01-272	NAP	SMEs	LU	EN AI Conformity assessment	LT	€ 10,000
45	7.57	01-196	NAP	Academia/Research	GR	Standardising large scale QKD networks and a Standardisation portal for Quantum Technologies	LT	€ 10,000
46	7.53	01-235	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	Standards for Next Generation of Information for Healthcare and Health Research AI-based	LT	€ 10,000
47	7.50	01-274	NAP	SMEs	DE	E-Invoicing/E-Procurement support at CEN TC 434/440 for innovation of the Digital Single Market	LT	€ 10,000
48	7.47	01-273	NAP	SMEs	FR	Supporting ISO/IEC 27031 editor for its revision project initiated 2020 til final publication	LT	€ 10,000
49	7.40	01-240	NAP	SMEs	BE	Participation in the standardisation work for the Cyber Resilience Act proposal	LT	€ 10,000
50	7.37	01-249	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	European Requirements for Face Biometric Products (ERBP-5)	LT	€ 10,000

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ¹	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
50	7.37	01-217	NAP	SMEs	AT	CEN/CLC/JTC 22/WG 4/WI "QKD and PQC – An equitable analysis and comparison of both technologies"(TR)	LT	€ 10,000
51	7.30	01-245	NAP	Academia/Research	LU	IoTDisco: Strong yet Lightweight End-to-End Security for the Internet of Constrained Things	ST	€ 10,000
51	7.30	01-200	NAP	Academia/Research	FR	Dynamic Context-Aware Access Control as a Service for Critical Infrastructure	LT	€ 10,000
52	7.27	01-268	NAP	Public-Private Partnership	BE	Standardization for green mobility - Saving the world	ST	€ 5,000
53	7.20	01-246	NAP	Academia/Research	PT	Contribution to new standard for autonomous robotic systems IEEE1872.3	LT	€ 10,000
54	7.17	01-204	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	ES	META4BIZ: Metaverse for Business Transformation, state-of-the-art and prospective Technical Report	LT	€ 10,000
55	7.15	01-101	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	ES	CYBERSECURITY CONTROLS APPLIED TO INFORMATION SYSTEMS INTERCONNECTED WITH AI SYSTEMS - PHASE I	ST	€ 5,000
56	7.10	01-183	NAP	Academia/Research	UK	Improving Trustworthiness of Internet Standards	LT	€ 10,000
56	7.10	01-229	NAP	SMEs	FR	Supporting ISO/IEC 27031 co-editor for its revision project initiated 2020 til final publication	LT	€ 10,000

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ¹	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
56	7.10	01-179	NAP	Academia/Research	NO	Non-Transparent Performance Enhancing Proxies for 6G	LT	€ 10,000
57	6.94	01-219	NAP	Academia/Research	IT	Iterative declarative workflows with the Common Workflow Language	LT	€ 10,000
58	6.93	01-255	NAP	Academia/Research	MK	Contribution to ISO/TC 307 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG	LT	€ 10,000
59	6.90	01-176	NAP	SMEs	AT	Lifts and Escalators in Smart Cities	LT	€ 10,000
60	6.85	01-244	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	ES	DGMQ - Enhancing Data Governance-Management-Quality through Standardization: Stage I, State of Art	LT	€ 10,000
61	6.80	01-191	NAP	Large Enterprise	DK	FINTECH IN SUSTAINABLE BANKING PRODUCTS AND SERVICES	LT	€ 10,000
62	6.73	01-184	NAP	Government/Public Services	BE	AI and cybersecurity standard development for the support of the AI act and CSA	LT	€ 10,000
63	6.67	01-152	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	Standardization works in AI: ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 [WG-3,WG-4] and CEN/CENELEC JTC21 [WG-1,WG-2,WG-3]	ST	€ 10,000
64	6.60	01-277	NAP	SMEs	FR	Harmonising Architectures in Decentralised Identity Standards at ISO/TC307	ST	€ 10,000
64	6.60	01-209	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	SI	HA-ITU-SG13-2H2023	LT	€ 10,000
64	6.60	01-114	NAP	Large Enterprise	DE	Automated Optimized Resource Allocation and Management in Coordinated Multi-Operator Environments	LT	€ 10,000

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ¹	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
65	6.40	01-206	NAP	Academia/Research	DE	Cities and Infrastructure: Smart infrastructures, climate change and sustainability	LT	€ 10,000
66	6.24	01-215	NAP	SMEs	ES	AI+CoE: Artificial Intelligence for Business powered by Centers of Excellence. Technical Report	LT	€ 10,000
67	6.22	01-214	NAP	Academia/Research	CY	Standard activities for the development of AI-ML based standard encoding/decoing video system	LT	€ 10,000
68	6.20	01-254	NAP	SMEs	ES	Contribution to European ICT standardization strategy and redesign of the governance model for ETSI	LT	€ 10,000
69	6.12	01-221	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	Pushing the Limits of Energy Efficiency in Mobile IoT Devices through Wake-up Radio (MobileWuR)	LT	€ 10,000
70	6.10	01-223	NAP	SMEs	FR	IoT Semantic Interoperability Specialization to Preventive Health, Well-Being and AI	LT	€ 10,000
71	6.05	01-260	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	Definition of Sustainable Digital Transformation	LT	€ 10,000
72	5.90	01-133	NAP	SMEs	IT	Standardization of an AI Framework in the context of Motion Picture audio and Data by AI (MPAI)	LT	€ 10,000
73	5.63	01-203	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	IT	SysML Reference Model for Model Based System and Software Engineers	LT	€ 10,000

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ¹	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
74	5.40	01-269	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	LT	Participation, contribution to ISO/IEC SC37 WG3, development of ISO/IEC 39794-2 finger format	ST	€ 10,000
75	5.34	01-257	NAP	Large Enterprise	ES	Circular economy standards in the industrial lift sector: open-code BIM standard and DPP adoption.	LT	€ 10,000
76	5.33	01-198	NAP	Academia/Research	TR	3GPP RAN WG2 5G Advanced Network Energy Saving	LT	€ 10,000
77	5.23	01-187	NAP	Academia/Research	IT	Standardizing Software-Implemented Hardware Fault Tolerance (SIHFT) approaches	LT	€ 10,000
78	4.90	01-281	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	SE	Convenor SC41/AG21 - Advisory Group for IoT and Digital Twins within Smart Cities and Utilities	LT	€ 10,000
79	3.73	01-280	NAP	SMEs	DE	Trusted Metadata standards for A/ML training data	ST	€ 10,000
80	3.10	01-266	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	For effective and efficient standardization	LT	€ 10,000
64	6.60	01-277	NAP	SMEs	FR	Harmonising Architectures in Decentralised Identity Standards at ISO/TC307	ST	€ 10,000
64	6.60	01-209	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	SI	HA-ITU-SG13-2H2023	LT	€ 10,000
64	6.60	01-114	NAP	Large Enterprise	DE	Automated Optimized Resource Allocation and Management in Coordinated Multi-Operator Environments	LT	€ 10,000

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ¹	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
65	6.40	01-206	NAP	Academia/Research	DE	Cities and Infrastructure: Smart infrastructures, climate change and sustainability	LT	€ 10,000
66	6.24	01-215	NAP	SMEs	ES	AI+CoE: Artificial Intelligence for Business powered by Centers of Excellence. Technical Report	LT	€ 10,000
67	6.22	01-214	NAP	Academia/Research	CY	Standard activities for the development of AI-ML based standard encoding/decoing video system	LT	€ 10,000
68	6.20	01-254	NAP	SMEs	ES	Contribution to European ICT standardization strategy and redesign of the governance model for ETSI	LT	€ 10,000
69	6.12	01-221	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	Pushing the Limits of Energy Efficiency in Mobile IoT Devices through Wake-up Radio (MobileWuR)	LT	€ 10,000
70	6.10	01-223	NAP	SMEs	FR	IoT Semantic Interoperability Specialization to Preventive Health, Well-Being and AI	LT	€ 10,000
71	6.05	01-260	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	Definition of Sustainable Digital Transformation	LT	€ 10,000
72	5.90	01-133	NAP	SMEs	IT	Standardization of an AI Framework in the context of Motion Picture audio and Data by AI (MPAI)	LT	€ 10,000
73	5.63	01-203	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	IT	SysML Reference Model for Model Based System and Software Engineers	LT	€ 10,000

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ¹	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
74	5.40	01-269	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	LT	Participation, contribution to ISO/IEC SC37 WG3, development of ISO/IEC 39794-2 finger format	ST	€ 10,000
75	5.34	01-257	NAP	Large Enterprise	ES	Circular economy standards in the industrial lift sector: open-code BIM standard and DPP adoption.	LT	€ 10,000
76	5.33	01-198	NAP	Academia/Research	TR	3GPP RAN WG2 5G Advanced Network Energy Saving	LT	€ 10,000
77	5.23	01-187	NAP	Academia/Research	IT	Standardizing Software-Implemented Hardware Fault Tolerance (SIHFT) approaches	LT	€ 10,000
78	4.90	01-281	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	SE	Convenor SC41/AG21 - Advisory Group for IoT and Digital Twins within Smart Cities and Utilities	LT	€ 10,000
79	3.73	01-280	NAP	SMEs	DE	Trusted Metadata standards for A/ML training data	ST	€ 10,000
80	3.10	01-266	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	For effective and efficient standardization	LT	€ 10,000

TABLE 5 – APPLICATIONS RECEIVED AND RANKED OC 1

4.2 Applications submitted and funded under OC 2

A full list of the eligible applications received to OC 2, including those not retained for funding, is provided in Table 6Table 1 below, in order of ranking with the proposal ID, the status of the fellowship at the time of writing, grant type and funding allocated

D3.1 Call Monitoring Report 1	 ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe
Grant Agreement No.: 101091933	

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
1	9.67	02-308	APR	SMEs	BE	Cybersecurity standards for AI systems in response to the EC standardisation request	LT	€ 10,000
1	9.57	02-360	APR	Academia/Research	GR	Large scale QKD and Quantum Networks best practices	LT	€ 10,000
2	9.20	02-303	APR	Academia/Research	ES	Rapid Electromagnetic Emission Check of Fixed Installations	LT	€ 9,980
3	9.13	02-340	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	DK	Key Management and Public-key infrastructure: Establishment and maintenance	LT	€ 9,900
4	9.07	02-359	APR	SMEs	FR	Integration of drivers (cybersecurity, privacy) and enablers (digital twins and IoT) in data spaces	LT	€ 10,000
5	9.04	02-369	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	BE	Contribution to e-identification and e-authentication at CEN/CLC/JTC 13 & ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 WG5's	ST	€ 4,950
6	9.00	02-391	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	DE	Progress Extensible Minutiae Standard ISO/IEC 39794-2	LT	€ 6,750

² APR -Approved; NAP – Not Approved; PAY – In Payment; CLO - Closed

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
6	9.00	02-382	APR	Academia/Research	ES	Standards for next generation of information for Healthcare and Research, AI Language Models-based	LT	€ 6,000
7	8.97	02-345	APR	SMEs	IT	DT-COOP: Standardizing Digital Twins Cooperation	LT	€ 8,960
8	8.93	02-336	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	UK	Study of IEC System committee use cases and their relevance to JTC 1 standardisation	LT	€ 9,900
8	8.93	02-363	APR	Academia/Research	FR	Towards accurate, transparent and explainable systems in AI and NLP, in support of the AI Act	LT	€ 6,170
9	8.80	02-387	APR	Academia/Research	LU	IoTDisco: Strong yet Lightweight End-to-End Security for the Internet of Constrained Things	ST	€ 5,000
10	8.73	02-311	APR	Academia/Research	UK	Core Standards for Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology and Digital Currencies	LT	€ 10,000
11	8.70	02-343	APR	SMEs	BE	Participation in the standardisation work at the ESOs for the Cyber Resilience Act proposal	LT	€ 10,000
12	8.67	02-298	APR	Academia/Research	ES	eID Wallet for the European citizen under the new eIDAS2	LT	€ 10,000

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
12	8.67	02-371	APR	Large Enterprise	DE	Multi-Criteria Allocation for Intelligent Sustainable Environments	Resource Poly-CSP LT	€ 8,299
12	8.67	02-380	APR	SMEs	BE	Protocols for cybersecurity evaluation and testing under RED cybersecurity essential requirements	LT	€ 10,000
13	8.60	02-348	APR	SMEs	UK	Technical Editor ISO/IEC 27566 Age Assurance Systems - Framework	LT	€ 9,800
14	8.57	02-352	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	GR	Develop use cases to inform new standards development in DLT & blockchain technologies	LT	€ 10,000
15	8.55	02-365	APR	SMEs	FR	Developing cybersecurity standardization for Artificial Intelligence and Internet of Things	LT	€ 10,000
15	8.55	02-374	APR	SMEs	FR	Bridging the gap between EU R&I ecosystem and worldwide standardization on Smart Energy	LT	€ 10,000
16	8.53	02-326	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	Navigating AI Ethics: Insights on AI Nudges, AI Competencies, Trust and Ethics Roadmap in EU	LT	€ 10,000
17	8.50	02-291	APR	SMEs	UK	Support to publication ETSI CYBER WI: Design practices against technology enabled coercive control	ST	€ 4,649

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
17	8.50	02-344	APR	Policy/Funding Agency	GR	Developing the ISO/TC307 Technical Committee Strategy for Standards Development in Blockchain & DLT	LT	€ 10,000
18	8.43	02-333	APR	SMEs	FR	Contribute to prISO 16757-5	LT	€ 10,000
18	8.43	02-377	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	LT	Advance on-card biometric comparison standards ISO/IEC 24787, ISO/IEC 17839, ISO/IEC 18584 series	LT	€ 6,300
19	8.40	02-300	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	ES	Standards for building simulation: new ontology for building simulation O4BSIM	LT	€ 9,720
20	8.35	02-372	APR	Academia/Research	PT	Contribution to new standard for autonomous robotic systems IEEE1872.3	LT	€ 10,000
21	8.29	02-379	APR	Not for Profit Organisation	NL	ISO/DIS 24138 – ISCC – International Standard Content Code	ST	€ 4,890
22	8.27	02-386	APR	SDO/National Standard Body	DE	Consumer-Centric Blockchain Standards: A Holistic Approach to DLT Identity and Security Protocols	LT	€ 9,900
23	8.23	02-362	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	NL	Bias testing expert in CEN/CLC/JTC 21 AI Working Groups 2-4 at national and international level	LT	€ 10,000
24	8.20	02-288	APR	SMEs	DE	Enhanced Interoperability of Spatio-Temporal Datacubes	LT	€ 9,900

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
25	8.15	02-355	APR	Academia/Research	ES	An information model for digital product passport information on sustainability and circularity	LT	€ 10,000
26	8.00	02-353	APR	SDO/National Standard Body	LT	Advance Biometric System-On-Card (ISO/IEC 17839) Standard improvement	LT	€ 4,950
27	7.97	02-385	APR	SMEs	FR	Managing last steps ISO/IEC 27031 revision, european experts and liaisons inputs within the project	LT	€ 10,000
27	7.97	02-317	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	UK	Advancing ISO/IEC 23000-23 Decentralised Media Rights Application Format	LT	€ 9,900
28	7.96	02-330	APR	SMEs	FR	Development of ITS geographic data standardisation for highly automated driving - Phase 3	LT	€ 10,000
29	7.80	02-299	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	European Requirements for the Evaluation of Face Biometric Products	LT	€ 10,000
30	7.77	02-350	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	DE	Standardization on Trustworthy Provable QTSP for Electronic Ledger (Section 11 eIDAS 2.0)	LT	€ 8,000
31	7.73	02-323	NAP	SMEs	FR	IoT Semantic Interoperability Methodology Demonstrated in Application Domains: Health, and Energy	LT	€ 10,000
32	7.70	02-364	NAP	SMEs	AT	QKD and PQC: An equitable analysis	LT	€ 10,000

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
33	7.66	02-295	NAP	SMEs	DE	Representation of domain-specific concepts in digital twins and other technical information assets	LT	€ 9,930
34	7.60	02-376	NAP	Academia/Research	SE	Extending the CSA Cloud Control Matrix with Confidential Computing	LT	€ 9,900
35	7.53	02-289	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	AT	Continued maintenance and shepherding of CBOR	LT	€ 9,850
36	7.40	02-378	NAP	Academia/Research	NO	Do away with customized system integrations - towards Open Command and Control	LT	€ 10,000
36	7.40	02-297	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	UK	Participation in standards development for Online Age Assurance ISO/IEEE/BSI/CEN-CENELEC	LT	€ 10,000
37	7.33	02-373	NAP	Academia/Research	FI	IoT, Edge and Security Standardization work in IETF and IRTF as an RFC Author and Designated Expert	LT	€ 10,000
37	7.33	02-368	NAP	SMEs	FR	Harmonising Architectures in Decentralised Identifier / Identity Standards at ISO/TC307	ST	€ 4,950
38	7.30	02-384	NAP	Academia/Research	IT	Standardizing the Quantum Internet	LT	€ 10,000
39	7.20	02-294	NAP	SMEs	AT	Lifts and Escalators in Smart Cities	LT	€ 9,650
40	7.17	02-322	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	BE	Green Mobility Standardization for smart and sustainable cities	LT	€ 9,975

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
41	7.03	02-388	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	DE	Consumer-Centric Blockchain Standards: A Holistic Approach to DLT Identity and Security Protocols	LT	€ 9,450
41	7.03	02-361	NAP	Not for Profit Organisation	DE	ISCC – International Standard Content Code	LT	€ 9,987
42	7.00	02-292	NAP	Academia/Research	IT	Use of the "C" programming language in critical systems	OS	€ 2,800
42	7.00	02-329	NAP	SMEs	UK	New networking technology to meet the requirements of 6G	LT	€ 10,000
43	6.95	02-325	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	LoRa Mesh Network Design and Applications	OS	€ 2,540
44	6.83	02-328	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	IT	Development of technical report "Data Governance & quality for AI in EU context" under JTC21-CEN/CLC	LT	€ 9,950
45	6.78	02-346	NAP	SMEs	UK	International standardisation for co-packaged optical assemblies	LT	€ 10,000
46	6.75	02-320	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	IT	Contributions to ISO artificial intelligence and cloud standards	LT	€ 10,000
47	6.73	02-349	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	ES	ISO/IEC/IEEE 26516 Design and development of instructional videos and animations	LT	€ 9,000
48	6.53	02-316	NAP	SMEs	ES	Alcoe: new standard in Artificial Intelligence powered by Center of Excellence. State of the art TR	LT	€ 9,000

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
49	6.50	02-356	NAP	SMEs	AT	Standardizing the did:keri method	LT	€ 9,600
49	6.50	02-390	NAP	SMEs	IT	Building an eco-system of trustworthiness for artificial intelligence	LT	€ 10,000
50	6.40	02-367	NAP	SMEs	IE	Preparation of proposal CEN Workshop to adapt ISO Blockchain DLT use case template for EU market.	ST	€ 5,000
51	6.23	02-313	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	SI	ITU-T SG13 2024	LT	€ 10,000
52	6.20	02-302	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	ES	Cybersecurity controls for Metaverse environments - Phase I State of the Art	ST	€ 4,800
53	6.17	02-357	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	DE	Defining the DPP Standards Request	LT	€ 3,600
54	6.00	02-301	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	ES	CYBERSECURITY CONTROLS APPLIED TO INFORMATION SYSTEMS INTERCONNECTED WITH AI SYSTEMS - PHASE I	ST	€ 4,800
55	6.00	02-370	NAP	SMEs	ES	Contribution to European ICT standardization strategy and redesign of the governance model for ETSI	LT	€ 10,000
56	5.90	02-327	NAP	Academia/Research	IT	Standards and digital maturity assessment for digital twins in E-healthcare	LT	€ 10,000
57	5.85	02-366	NAP	SMEs	NO	Metaverse as a digital learning environment	LT	€ 9,900

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
58	5.80	02-381	NAP	SMEs	FR	Supporting ISO/IEC 27031 co-editor for its revision project initiated 2020 til final publication	LT	€ 10,000
58	5.80	02-321	NAP	Academia/Research	NO	Non-Transparent Performance Enhancing Proxies for 6G	LT	€ 7,300
59	5.57	02-338	NAP	Academia/Research	MK	Contribution to ISO/TC 307 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG	LT	€ 9,900
60	5.40	02-337	NAP	SMEs	UK	Delivering the open 3D web	LT	€ 10,000
61	5.27	02-375	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	AT	Radio regulations for wireless technologies	LT	€ 9,850
62	5.10	02-389	NAP	Academia/Research	DE	Specify Security Goals of AI Systems in International and European Standardisation (CEN JTC21)	ST	€ 7,000
63	5.07	02-307	NAP	Academia/Research	FI	Contribution to ETSI TC SmartBAN	LT	€ 10,000
64	4.87	02-305	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	ES	M4BT: Industrialising the Metaverse for Business Transformation. Implementation state-of-the-art TR	LT	€ 9,900
65	4.43	02-309	NAP	SMEs	RO	Contribute to cybersecurity standards for Smart Cities	LT	€ 10,000
66	4.40	02-358	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	Intergenerational digital service-learning Hackathons around Europe	LT	€ 10,000
67	4.20	02-335	NAP	Government/Public Services	NO	Work within the 3GPP SA3-LI, including meetings	LT	€ 9,990

D3.1 Call Monitoring Report 1	 ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe
Grant Agreement No.: 101091933	

Rank	Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
68	3.50	02-312	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	Standarization works as AI Normative Expert (ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42, CEN/CENELEC JTC1, UNE CTN71 SC42)	OS	€ 3,000

TABLE 6 – APPLICATIONS RECEIVED AND RANKED OC

5. MONITORING OF THE FUNDED FELLOWS AND IMPACT

5.1 Monitoring Methodology

The monitoring of the funded fellowships (Task 3.2) is managed by AUS who manage the design and implementation the monitoring strategy. The monitoring methodology includes two parts: the follow-up of the individual fellowships ensuring that all funded projects meet the set objectives and results, and the impact assessment of the entire fellowship programme, as shown in Figure 12.

FIGURE 12 FELLOWSHIP MONITORING STRATEGY

The StandICT.eu 2026 Fellowship Programme monitoring is supported by the Logical Framework Approach (LFA) which permits analysis and organisation of the gathered monitoring information in a structured way. Within this framework, the following project aspects are controlled:

- Identification of successes and problems during the fellowship implementation;
- Informed and timely decision making by project manager to support the implementation;
- Accountability for the activity and results achieved;
- Fellows' contribution to the dissemination of the results and participation in the StandICT.eu 2026 Programme;
- Assessment and validation of the fellowship's achievements and activities.

For the One-Shot and Short-term fellowships (up to 3 months) two monitoring elements are requested: the fellowship work plan (defined in the application), and the final report (submitted for the project end date).

For the Long-Term fellowships (up to 6 months) three monitoring elements are requested: the fellowship work plan (defined in the application) the interim report (submitted in the mid-term of the project) and the final report (submitted for the project end date).

The StandICT.eu team reviews all submitted reports ensuring that these meet the set quality requirements (i.e., all report questions are responded to, with full and relevant responses, and that it clearly states the major results of the fellowship and the potential impact of the stakeholders). Once the final report is validated by AUS and Trust-IT team members, DCU manages the grant payment process. The fellowship stories and results are shared in StandICT.eu's communication channels (website, social media, and newsletters), and, under each open call batch, we publish an impact report showcasing the individual fellowship profiles, addressed standards, and achieved results. Moreover, Figure 13 outlines the monitoring process steps.

FIGURE 13 FELLOWSHIP MONITORING PROCESS

5.2 Monitoring Tools

The TRUST-GRANTS™ platform³ enables to implement the LFA in practice and to track down all the required fellowship data. Moreover, to gather the fellowship performance data, the funded fellows are requested to submit their fellowship reports within the set deadlines. In addition, AUS manages an internal database tracking the reporting deadlines and submissions. These two tools, combined with regular one-to-one communication with the funded fellows ensure that all reporting is done respecting the set deadlines and quality criteria.

ID	Call	Title	User	Organisation	Organisation Type	Creation date	Submission date	Workflow	Evaluated	Actions
01-099	StandICT.eu 2026 - 1st Open Call	Accessibility in the Metaverse	Pilar Orero	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	Academia/Research	09/05/2023 - 14.43	10/05/2023 - 09.01	Approved	Yes	⋮
01-105	StandICT.eu 2026 - 1st Open Call	Launching generalized quantum cryptography standardization	Witold Jacak	European Information Technologies Certification Institute	SDQ/National Standard Body	10/05/2023 - 12.55	09/07/2023 - 22.55	Approved	Yes	⋮
01-111	StandICT.eu 2026 - 1st Open Call	Phase-2 STD Gen Framework: X-Dom Federated ETSI GANA KPs for 5G E2E Autonomic Security Man & Control	Ranganai Chaparadza	Altran Caggemini Germany	IT Consultancy/Development	11/05/2023 - 00.09	19/05/2023 - 01.08	Approved	Yes	⋮
01-117	StandICT.eu 2026 - 1st Open Call	Support as Secretary for ETSI ISO SAI	Alex Gadzow	Cadzow Communications Consulting Ltd.	Small and Medium Enterprise	15/05/2023 - 13.27	17/05/2023 - 14.07	Approved	Yes	⋮
01-118	StandICT.eu 2026 - 1st Open Call	Advance Biometric System-on-Card standard series ISO/IEC 17839	Robert MUELLER	Dr. Robert Mueller IT Consulting	IT Consultancy/Development	15/05/2023 - 17.20	15/05/2023 - 17.20	Approved	Yes	⋮
01-143	StandICT.eu 2026 - 1st Open Call	Harmonised AI cybersecurity standards in response to the EC AI standardisation request	Francisco Medeiros-Filho	FM Tech Consult BV	Small and Medium Enterprise	25/05/2023 - 19.06	20/06/2023 - 14.40	Approved	Yes	⋮
01-144	StandICT.eu 2026 - 1st Open Call	Environmental Sustainability for Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies	Belen Suarez	Reaccion Economica	Academia/Research	25/05/2023 - 19.52	19/06/2023 - 19.02	Approved	Yes	⋮
01-166	StandICT.eu 2026 - 1st Open Call	Progress projects on logging and record keeping to support the AI Act	Adam Smith	Dragonfly	IT Consultancy/Development	30/05/2023 - 14.55	30/05/2023 - 15.35	Approved	Yes	⋮
01-180	StandICT.eu 2026 - 1st Open Call	Standards for information security and cloud service providers	Karim Tobich	CyberSecurity & Technology Consultancy Ltd	IT Consultancy/Development	04/06/2023 - 20.13	04/06/2023 - 20.13	Approved	Yes	⋮
01-181	StandICT.eu 2026 - 1st Open Call	Advancing the PWI on Competence Requirements for AI Ethics Professionals to the NWP stage	Alessio Tartaro	University of Sassari	Academia/Research	06/06/2023 - 15.40	06/06/2023 - 15.40	Approved	Yes	⋮

FIGURE 14 TRUST-GRANTS REPORTING PLATFORM

The fellowship report structure includes two sections:

- Section 1: draws the Fellowship Profile (Bio, expertise in standardisation)
- Section 2: focuses on the Progress Reporting including Addressed gaps, priorities and standards, Delivered results (events, meetings, reports), Impact on society and SMEs, Status & Next steps.

The interim and final reports both follow the same structure; the interim report is shorter and it aims at ensuring that the fellowship is progressing according to the work plan provided in the fellowship application. Whereas, the final report includes more requestions regarding the project impact; the resulting revised or new standards, resulting publications etc.

³ <https://grants2026.standict.eu/>

Section 2 - Progress Reporting

2.1 Indicate which gaps, priorities or challenges you are addressing? Please describe these three aspects *

[limit 2000 char]

2.2 How is your funded application contributing to the ICT Standards landscape, and can you name the ICT Standards you are dealing with? *

[limit 2000 char]

2.3 Are you a contributor to a Working Group WG (s) or Technical Committee TC (s) as a part of your fellowship? If yes, please name it. *

Yes
 No

2.4 Does your contribution impact European SMEs and/or European societies? If yes, please elaborate *

Yes
 No

2.5 In the framework of your fellowship, have you collaborated with any other Associations or any EU or national project(s)? If yes, please elaborate. *

Yes
 No

2.6 Is your project directly involved or leading to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards? *

Yes
 No

2.7 What is the current status of your contribution? *

FIGURE 15 EXTRACT FROM THE FELLOWSHIP REPORT TEMPLATE

5.3 Current Monitoring Status of the Fellowship Programme

Open Call #1 fellowships have been monitored since September 2023. In this batch, a total of 35 fellowships were awarded, 17% of these fellowships are carried out by women, and 29% of the funded experts are new to the programme (i.e., they have not participated in the earlier funding batches of StandICT.eu). Moreover, 62% contribute to international standardisation organisations, including ISO, ISO/IEC, IEC, ITU, IEEE, and IETF; the remainder contributes to ESOs (ETSI, CEN or CEN/CENELEC) or to cross-SDO collaboration.

As shown in Figure 16 and Figure 17, the majority of the OC#1 fellows have passed the interim phase of their fellowship and are working on the second half of their project.

FIGURE 16 OC 1 INTERIM REPORTING STATUS

FIGURE 17 OC 1 FINAL REPORTING STATUS

Open Call #2 fellowship monitoring was launched in mid-December, and the first reports will be submitted in the end of December 2023.

6. NEXT STEPS

Given that OC 3 is due to close in January 2024, in the immediate term the new members accepted to the EPE will be onboarded via contract and the evaluations of OC3 launched.

Closure and announcement of the outcome of OC3 will also see the launch of the third batch of projects and start to reveal any significant trends in the statistics gathered in terms of topic coverage and SDOs.

The following months will also foresee closure of the majority of the fellowships launched under OC1 and, therefore, the impact generated in this first batch of fellows and publication of the first of the "[Following the Fellows](#)" series of publications for StandICT.eu 2026 project initiated under the pre-cursor StandICT.eu 2023 project, a user-powered series of publications to showcase the most relevant outcomes, creating awareness of the potential impact of the funded activities and its repercussions on commerce, industry, governmental policies and strategies and society as the fellows from the second batch of mainly long-term activities will reach also the Interim Reporting stage.

As an outcome of the StandICT.eu 2023 review, it was agreed that there should be greater awareness of activities funded by StandICT.eu within the relevant SDOs. Therefore, from OC3 each corresponding Working Group or Technical Committee Chair or Co Chair will be informed of funding provided to experts through StandICT.eu to support activities within the SDO, except in those cases where the funding is in support of the Chair or Co-Chair, which is often the case. In addition, a list of the new fellows will be posted to the website upon release of the OC3 results and retroactively from OC1 with information on the SDOs to whom the fellow is contributing.

Finally, while StandICT.eu has a well-consolidated, and seamless workflow surrounding the open calls, the team will continue to monitor this closely and make any adjustments as necessary as part of the continuous improvement of the process.
